

Supporting Information to accompany:

Adapting (4,4) Networks Through Substituent effects and Conformationally Flexible 3,2':6',3"-Terpyridines

Dalila Rocco, Alessandro Prescimone, Edwin C. Constable and Catherine E. Housecroft*

Department of Chemistry, University of Basel, Mattenstrasse 24a, BPR 1096, 4058 Basel, Switzerland

Fig. S1. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.5n\text{CHCl}_3$

Fig. S2. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.3n\text{CHCl}_3$

Fig. S3. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{3})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4n\text{CHCl}_3$

Fig. S4. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{4})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n$

Fig. S5. Solid-state IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{5})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot n\text{CHCl}_3$

Fig. S6. Overlay of the experimental PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.3n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Fig. S7. Overlay of the experimental PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.5n\text{CHCl}_3$.

Fig. S8. Overlay of the experimental PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{4})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n$.

Fig. S9. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{1})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.5n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry related atoms. Symmetry codes: $i = 3/2 - y, x, z$; $ii = y, 3/2 - x, z$; $iii = 1 - y, 1 - x, 1/2 - z$; $iv = 1 - x, -1/2 + y, 1/2 - z$. H atoms and solvent molecules are omitted. Ellipsoids are plotted at 40% probability level.

Fig. S10. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.3n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry related atoms. The biphenyl unit is disordered (see text) and only one position is shown. Symmetry codes: $i = y, 1/2 - x, z$; $ii = 1/2 - y, x, z$; $iii = -1/2 + y, 1/2 + x, 3/2 - z$; $iv = -1/2 + x, 1 - y, 3/2 - z$. H atoms and solvent molecules omitted. Ellipsoids are plotted at 40% probability level.

Fig. S11. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{3})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry related atoms. H atoms and solvent molecules omitted. Ellipsoids are plotted at 40% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $1-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; ii = $1/2+x, 1-y, 3/2-z$; iii = $1-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; iv = $-1/2+x, 1-y, 3/2-z$.

Fig. S12. Part of one 2D-sheet in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4.3n\text{CHCl}_3$ showing cones above and below the plane containing the Co atoms. H atoms and solvent molecules are omitted.

Fig. S13. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{3})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 4n\text{CHCl}_3$ (cycle 2: after 24 hour exposure to CHCl_3 vapor). Green: temperature vs. time; blue: weight of sample vs. time; red: mass detection for m/z 83.0 (most intense peak), 85.0 and 87.0. The initial mass of sample was 3.60 mg and a weight loss of 0.68 mg corresponds to ca. 19%.

Fig. S14. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{3})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot 2n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 2n\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (cycle 4: after 24 hours exposure to CH_2Cl_2 vapor). Green: temperature vs. time; blue: weight of sample vs. time; red: mass detection for m/z 49.0, 51.0, 84.0, 86.0. The initial mass of sample was 2.26 mg and a weight loss of 0.28 mg corresponds to ca. 12%.

Fig. S15. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{4})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n$ with symmetry related atoms. H atoms and solvent molecules omitted. Ellipsoids are plotted at 40% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1/2+x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $ii = -1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $iii = -x, -y, 1-z$; $iv = -1/2+x, 1/2-y, -1/2+z$; $v = 1/2+x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$.

Fig. S16. Structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{5})_2(\text{NCS})_2]_n \cdot n\text{CHCl}_3$ with symmetry related atoms. H atoms and solvent molecules omitted. Ellipsoids are plotted at 40% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 5/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $ii = 3/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $iii = 5/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $iv = 3/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$.